

A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL TOURISM MARKET

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Abstract: The theoretical foundations of the development of the tourism sector are researched in the article based on the study of the systems theory and the systematic approach to development.

Key words: tourism, tourism market, systems theory, systemic approach, emergence, commutativity, hierarchy.

The tourism market is a complex, developing, improving open system consisting of a set of multifaceted, interconnected elements. In this system, the presence of elements that are fundamentally different from each other in terms of content and content, their multifaceted interactions, as well as the interaction and influence of the system with the environment, as well as the manifestation of various unique characteristics as a result of its functioning as a whole, indicate its complexity.

A systematic approach to the concept of the development of the regional tourism market is based, first of all, on the complex description of tourist activity, on the specificity of mutual socio-economic relations within the framework of various sectors of the national economy, and also on the fact that it is a component of a huge macro-system in the form of "economy - society - environment" comes out. The elements of the tourism market system exhibit the "integrity" characteristic of the system, primarily due to their actions in integrity and compatibility through their interactions and interactions. It is this integrity that ensures the existence of the system called the tourism market and its effective operation.

Systematic approach to science was introduced for the first time at the beginning of the 20th century by the Russian scientist A.A. Bogdanov. However, the science of "Tectology" about the systematic approach proposed by him did not find its practical application due to the requirements of the times. Later, in the early 20s of the 20th century, a young biologist, Ludwig Bertalanffy, studied biological organisms as systems and embodied his views on systems in his 1929 work entitled "The Modern Theory of Development". Later, he used the systematic approach to the analysis of social phenomena and processes, and through the work "General Systems Theory" published in 1969, he managed to introduce his theory into science as a general theoretical science. L. in the formation and development of the theory of systems. Bertalanfi, A.A. Scientists such as Bogdanov, U. Ashby, G. Simon, P. Druker, A. Chandler¹ made a great contribution.

¹ *Богданов А.А.* Всеобщая организационная наука: тектология: в 2 кн. А.А. Богданов. – М., 1905 – 1924.; *Берталанфи Л. фон.* Общая теория систем — обзор проблем и результатов. Системные исследования. Ежегодник. — М.: «Наука», 1969. — 203с., С.34-35.; *Берталанфи Л. Фон.* История и статус общей теории систем / Берталанфи Л. Фон // Системные исследования: ежегодник. — М.: Наука, 1973. — С. 20 – 37.; *Эшби У. Р.* Введение в кибернетику: пер. с англ. / под. ред. В. А. Успенского. Предисл. А. Н. Колмогорова. Изд. 2-е,

Stanford Optner, the head of a large research laboratory named "S.L. Optner & Associates" in the USA, was one of the first to substantiate the possibilities, specific aspects and characteristics of effective use of systematic approaches in the process of organization management, and he cited these views in his work entitled "Systematic Approach", published in 1969. In the introduction and development of the systematic approach and systematic views in economic teaching, representatives of the "New School of Management Science" founded in 1950 (L.Bertalanfi, A.Rapoport, R.Akoff, R.Kalman, M.Mesarovich, S.Bir, V.Leontev etc.) has a large contribution. The scientific-theoretical views and concepts specific to this school were formed on the basis of scientific achievements in the field of electronic computing techniques, economic-mathematical methods and simulation models. They applied the methods of exact sciences to the analysis process, using general systems theory as the main basis for researching management activities. Systematic approach and systematic analysis served as the main paradigm of this school.

During the formation and development of the theory of systems, the concept of "system" was interpreted in the form of similar definitions in various scientific literature. In particular: "a set of interrelated and unified elements", "a set of elements interrelated with each other and their attributes", "a set of elements organized in such a way that the change, removal or introduction of a new element is legally reflected in other elements", "a set of objects with systematic properties, and a set of relations between objects and their properties", "a whole consisting of parts; integrity and unity as a result of the combination of elements that are in contact with each other", "a set of interconnected elements that form a stable integrity and unity with integral properties and laws", "mutually supporting each other in order to obtain a useful result in the focus of their interaction and interaction" Definitions such as "a set of selectively involved components" can be given.

The Russian scientist L.I. Lopatnikov defined the concept of economic system as "... a component of a socio-economic system that is relatively higher than itself. This is a complex dynamic system covering the processes of production, exchange, distribution, and consumption of material goods. interpreted as

Thus, based on the analysis of the definitions that reveal the essence of the concept of "system", the following cases specific to the system can be distinguished:

- the system is formed, operates and develops under the influence of certain factors;
- the system consists of a specific structural composition (organizational, economic, social, production, etc.);
- consists of a set of elements that realize specific goals through their activity as a whole;
- consists of a set of methods, tools, and algorithms that implement the system between elements, in other words, a mechanism that implements systematic connections.

стереотипное. — М.: «КомКнига», 2005.; *Эшби У. Р.* Общая теория систем как новая научная дисциплина. В кн.: Исследования по общей теории систем. Сборник переводов. М.: «Прогресс», 1969, с.125-142; *Эшби У.Р.* Принципы самоорганизации. В кн.: Принципы самоорганизации. Пер. с англ. Под ред. и с предисловием д-ра техн. наук А. Я. Лернера, М.: «Мир», 1966, с.314-343.

As a conclusion, it should be emphasized that "many elements forming a clear whole" and "coherence of many elements with clear common characteristics" reveal the essence of the concept of system and reflect the limits and conditions of its development. These properties are interpreted as the "law of emergence" and "law of additivity" in systems theory and systematic analysis, respectively.

In addition, one of the laws of system operation based on the theory of systems is the law of commutativity. Based on this law, "it (the system) creates a unique unity with the environment..., ... and is connected with the environment through various communications." The boundaries between the environment and the system may change during the period of object study. Depending on the different stages of development, new correlations between the elements of the system and the environment can be formed, and thus the transfer of elements from the system to the environment or from the environment to the system can be observed.

Thus, systems operate in the period from the state in which their elements are characterized by strictly centralized relations to the state of complete disruption of these relations.

Systematic approach is a direction of research methodology based on considering the object under study as a set of elements as a whole and a set of interactions between them, that is, as a system².

Based on these approaches, the study of the regional tourism market creates an opportunity to study its system characteristics. We would like to mention a number of unique features of the regional tourism market as a system. Based on these approaches, the study of the regional tourism market creates an opportunity to study its system characteristics. We would like to mention a number of unique features of the regional tourism market as a system. Because the implementation and realization of these features is important for the full implementation of the regional tourism market.

First, the regional tourism market is an open economic system. The "openness" of the regional tourism market as a system results from its high level of connection with the external environment. The existing socio-economic relations in the modern tourism market are being formed and developing on the basis of the processes of globalisation. In such conditions, in our opinion, the role and importance of current socio-economic relations in the tourism market are formed and developed under the influence of various exogenous and endogenous, static and dynamic, extensive and intensive, positive and negative, as well as seasonal factors specific to this market. .

Secondly, the characteristic of "commutability" of an open system leads to the change of boundaries between the external environment and the system and the exchange of mutual elements. This causes the system to develop and improve itself. The process of globalization, scientific and technological progress, improvement of the transport system improves the regional tourism markets and more fully demonstrates the feature of "commutability" characteristic of the system.

Thirdly, the "emergency" feature of the regional tourism market system shows that it is fundamentally different from other systems. "Emergent" property is not specific to individual

² Печатникова С.М. Системное управление «по образу и подобию» как фактор выживания предприятия на рынке // Менеджмент в России и за рубежом – 2005. - №3. - с. 11-17.

elements of the system and only arises as a result of actions of these elements as a whole in a single system. The development of the tourism market affects the economic status of a number of organizations of the economic sector, which are participants of complex socio-economic relations in this market, and thereby creates a multiplier effect. Multiplicative efficiency is a characteristic of this system that expresses the wholeness and unity.

Fourthly, the regional tourism market as a whole system embodies the integrated actions of various organizations specializing in "supplying a tourist product with a complex description to the consumer".

Fifth, the regional tourism market as a complex system also shows the characteristic of "hierarchy". The "hierarchy" of the system is based on considering each of its constituent elements as constituent parts (systems) of a broader system (for example, national tourism market, international tourism market).

Thus, the uniqueness of the regional tourism market is determined by the characteristics of the natural-geographical, socio-economic, ethnographic, material-technical, and political aspects of the relevant area with its geographical scope, and it has a management system that regulates its development.

Sixth, the regional tourism market is considered to have a complex and structural description characteristic of an open economic system. This structural classification is from the following, namely:

- system of socio-economic relations;
- organizational and legal forms of economic management;
- market mechanism;
- incentive and motivation system of market entities;
- consists of the integrity and integrity of such elements as the infrastructure of the tourism market.

If we conclude from the above points, the effective development of the regional tourism market depends on the effective and rational use of natural-recreational, financial, labor, and information resources by private business entities and the state in mutual cooperation.

In order to achieve the necessary results in the development of the regional tourism market, it is necessary to be based on the following principles: inter-sectoral cooperation and compatibility; functional integration and compatibility; hierarchical cohesion and compatibility; cooperative activity in the tourism market.

The tourism industry appears as a complex interdisciplinary complex that unites various sectors of the national economy. The competitiveness of regional tourism products in the international tourism market requires cooperative activities based on the principle of inter-sectoral cooperation and compatibility.

Subjects of the regional tourism market conduct their activities independently of each other by offering separate parts of the tourist product, but perform essentially the same tasks in order to achieve effective results in the market (for example, marketing activities). Their effective operation in the market depends on the market competitiveness of the integrated

tourism product offered by them. This situation requires these organizations to operate on the basis of the principle of functional integration and compatibility in the market (for example, cooperative advertising activities).

Based on the principle of hierarchical cohesion and compatibility, it is necessary to develop a plan of appropriate measures for the development of the tourism market on the basis of mutual cohesion and compatibility at all levels of state power. For this reason, the state's programs regulating the development of tourism in a certain area should be reflected in all programs of the socio-economic development of the area.

Based on the principle of cooperative activity in the tourism market, it is possible to achieve the effective development of the regional tourism market by establishing strong cooperative relations between the state and private business, private business and science.

The above-mentioned principles of effective development of the regional tourism market, in our opinion, are reflected in the theoretical aspects of development based on systems theory and a systematic approach. Therefore, the description of the regional tourism market as a complex multifaceted system leads to a systematic approach to its development. This, in turn, requires the actions of the elements of this system to be more effective than their relatively disorganized actions. Each system is characterized by its own set of elements, its structural description, relationships between elements, their interaction methods, and their interaction and influence with the external environment.

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